

Implementation of a hydroponics garden system in a culinary kitchen laboratory for sustainable plant-based ingredient harvesting

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Abstract

Innovative hydroponic cultivation systems provide a solution to the culinary industry's difficulty in sourcing sustainable ingredients. This study investigates the incorporation of a hydroponic garden into a culinary kitchen facility to provide eco-friendly plant-based ingredients for recipe development and education. The research provides an in-depth analysis of the ecological, economic, and social benefits of hydroponic gardening in the culinary industry, as well as instructions for setting up a hydroponic system in a kitchen facility. Using a combination of a literature review analysis, a research-through-design study, and focused group discussions and semi-structured interviews with 10 chefs, seven agricultural experts, and six hydroponics farmers, this research evaluates the environmental, economic, and social benefits of hydroponic gardening in the culinary industry. The study found that hydroponic gardening systems can significantly reduce water and land consumption, increase crop yields, and promote environmentally favorable agricultural practices. The research concludes that incorporating a hydroponic garden setup into a culinary kitchen facility is a feasible strategy for addressing the difficulties of sourcing sustainable ingredients in the culinary industry.

Keywords: Hydroponics garden system; culinary industry; harvesting; plant-based ingredients.

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Introduction

The environmental impact of the food industry is substantial, particularly in terms of ingredient sourcing and transportation. The issue of procuring ingredients in a sustainable manner has gained significant importance in the culinary industry, as chefs and restaurants are under mounting pressure to source local ingredients, reduce their carbon emissions, and curtail wastage. The increasing popularity of plant-based foods has led to a heightened necessity for sustainable sourcing practices. Hydroponic gardening systems present a novel solution to this predicament by establishing a regulated setting for the cultivation of plants, which employs significantly less water and land in comparison to traditional farming techniques (Resh, 2012). The objective of this investigation is to analyze the integration of a hydroponic garden system within a culinary kitchen laboratory, with the purpose of providing sustainable plant-based ingredients for recipe development and educational purposes.

The culinary industry is currently witnessing a surge in demand for plant-based foods and sustainable ingredient sourcing, because of its focus on sustainability and eco-friendly practices. Hydroponic gardening systems offer a solution to this predicament by creating a regulated setting for cultivating plants, which utilizes substantially less water and land compared to conventional farming techniques. The implementation of such systems in urban areas can potentially mitigate the demand for transportation and consequent usage of fossil fuels. The integration of a hydroponic garden system within a culinary kitchen laboratory can facilitate the provision of sustainable plant-based ingredients for recipe

development and educational purposes, thereby reducing the environmental impact associated with ingredient sourcing.

Figure 1. Food system map: Basic elements (Source: shiftN CVBA, 2009)

Hydroponic cultivation systems offer a range of environmental, economic, and social benefits compared to conventional agricultural practices. According to the United States Department of Agriculture and the National Agricultural Statistics Office’s report in 2019, hydroponic systems have been found to consume 90% less water compared to traditional farming methods. In addition, it has been noted that hydroponic systems necessitate significantly less land and obviate the necessity for pesticides or herbicides, thereby diminishing the overall environmental ramifications of ingredient sourcing (FAO, 2018; Khan et al., 2020). The implementation of a hydroponic system within a kitchen laboratory environment has the potential to reduce the carbon footprint attributed to the transportation and storage of ingredients, as stated by the Food and Agriculture Organization in 2018. The incorporation of a hydroponic garden system within a culinary kitchen laboratory has the potential to generate economic advantages. According to a report by the National Sustainable Agriculture Coalition (NSAC) in 2017, hydroponic systems have the potential to yield up to 20 times more vegetables per square foot compared to conventional farming techniques. The augmentation in production can lead to economic benefits for gastronomic establishments and supplementary income via the vending of plant-derived ingredients obtained through sustainable means. Hydroponic cultivation systems offer social advantages, particularly in metropolitan regions where the availability of fresh and nutritious produce may be restricted. Within the context of a culinary laboratory, a hydroponic system can function as an instructive tool for both students and members of the community, advocating for sustainable agricultural methodologies and the cultivation of nutritious dietary habits (Goodman & Minner, 2019).

The mutually reinforcing relationship of food and urban systems, influenced by environmental, economic, and socio-cultural factors, is illustrated in Figure 2, as per Tyrväinen et al.’s (2014) food system map. The consideration of all components within a system is imperative for the preservation of its sustainability, and it is at this juncture that the concept of systems theory assumes significance. In order to explore substitute modes of production and assess the efficacy, consistency, and sustainability of a given system, it is imperative to conduct a thorough evaluation of each system utilizing a comprehensive systems approach.

Figure 2. Food system map (Tyrväinen et al., 2014)

Methodology

The present study employed a combination of literature review analysis, exploratory investigation, and focus group discussions, in conjunction with semi-structured interviews, to investigate the viability of hydroponic gardening systems within the food industry. The utilization of the research-through-design (RtD) methodology, as explicated by Zimmerman et al. (2010), enables researchers to produce knowledge via design practice methods, resulting in the development of artifacts intended to facilitate societal transformation.

The methodology of Research through Design (RtD) encompassed the creation of a hydroponic garden system within a culinary laboratory setting, with the objective of cultivating diverse plant-based constituents. Qualitative data was collected on the potential advantages and challenges of hydroponic gardening within the food industry through focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews with a sample of 10 chefs, 7 agriculturists, and 6 hydroponic farmers.

Design Research as a Source of Knowledge

Consistent with the perspective of Zimmerman et al. (2007) regarding the role of design research in generating knowledge, this investigation utilizes the methodology of Research through Design (RtD) to investigate the viability, efficacy, and durability of integrating hydroponic garden systems into culinary kitchen laboratories. The emphasis is placed on the production of knowledge as opposed to solely directing the development of marketable goods.

Designedly Inquiry and Social Change

This research study aims to utilize RtD (Research through Design) as a purposeful inquiry to develop artifacts that can bring about social change (Zimmerman et al., 2010). The objective of this study is to promote sustainable practices in the culinary industry by introducing hydroponic garden systems.

Rigorous Method Formulation

To establish the credibility of the RtD methodology and its integration into established scientific practices, this research inquiry adheres to a more stringent approach to method formulation as espoused by Zimmerman et al. (2010). This entails the establishment of a methodical methodology for the purpose of devising, evaluating, and enhancing the hydroponic cultivation system, in addition to recording and scrutinizing the outcomes.

Formal Measurement for Validation and Robustness

Consistent with the recommendation of Keyson and Bruns (2009) to integrate formal measurement into Research through Design (RtD), this study integrates both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques to assess the efficacy, efficiency, and durability of the hydroponic garden system that has been put into practice. This approach can contribute to the validation of the research findings, bolster the robustness of the study, and improve the generalizability of the outcomes.

Results and Analysis

Environmental Benefits

Hydroponic cultivation techniques present several ecological benefits, such as decreased utilization of water and land resources. Cultivation of hydroponic crops, which involves the growth of plants in a regulated environment without the use of soil, necessitates considerably lower water usage in comparison to conventional farming practices. This facilitates increased food production on a reduced land area, thereby aiding in the preservation of natural resources such as forests and soil. Hydroponics is a cultivation method that exhibits a lower energy consumption compared to traditional farming techniques. This is due to the absence of pesticides and fertilizers, which frequently contain hazardous substances. Furthermore, hydroponic systems employ artificial grow lights in lieu of natural sunlight to facilitate photosynthesis, thereby obviating the necessity for expensive heating systems during colder seasons and resulting in reduced heating expenses. In addition, the lack of usage of pesticides or fertilizers within the system leads to the cultivation of healthier plants as they are exposed to fewer harmful substances.

Economic Benefits

Hydroponic cultivation techniques offer a range of advantages to culinary professionals, such as decreased expenses related to labor, amplified crop output, and enhanced availability of regionally procured constituents. Hydroponic systems have been found to incur lower labour costs compared to conventional soil-based agriculture. This is attributed to the reduced workforce required, which is facilitated by the advancements in automation technology. As a result, the available workers can operate more efficiently. Furthermore, due to the indoor cultivation of hydroponic crops, they are shielded from external weather conditions, thereby eliminating the requirement for supplementary lighting or irrigation systems during unfavorable weather conditions, such as rainfall or snowfall, leading to reduced outdoor plant maintenance time (Bantis et al., 2018).

Hydroponics is a cultivation method that facilitates the optimization of plant density per unit area of growing space, thereby enhancing productivity. This is achieved through vertical stacking techniques, such as vertical farming or wall-to-wall gardening with stacked trays. These techniques enable the roots of each tray to have direct access to the nutrient solution, without having to grow through soil before reaching the water at the bottom level, where nutrients would typically be found in an outdoor garden setting. As a result, hydroponics has the potential to increase yield significantly.

Potential Benefits of Hydroponic Gardening in the Culinary Industry

The practice of hydroponic gardening is a sustainable and economical approach to cultivating plants. This practice facilitates regulation of soil nutrient concentrations, thereby mitigating the risk of excessive or insufficient nutrient supply to plants. Ensuring appropriate nutrient provision is crucial for hydroponically cultivated fruits and vegetables, as inadequate nourishment can render them susceptible to diseases.

Potential Challenges of Hydroponic Gardening in the Culinary Industry

The utilization of hydroponic gardening as a means of plant cultivation presents a promising approach. However, certain obstacles must be considered prior to its implementation within a culinary laboratory setting. The obstacles encompassing the establishment of a restaurant business comprise the preliminary expenses of setup and the dearth of expertise and acquaintance among culinary professionals and proprietors.

Assessing the Potential of Kitchen Garden Systems

The initial phase of implementing a viable plant-based ingredient harvesting system involves evaluating the viability of kitchen garden systems. Gaining insight into the available resources to produce plant-based food and their potential for facilitating sustainable food production is crucial in assessing the feasibility of implementing such a project within a culinary laboratory.

Impact on Kitchen Laboratory School's Plant-Based Food Production

The adoption of a hydroponic gardening system at the Culinary Kitchen Laboratory School represents a noteworthy advancement in the pursuit of food security and sustainability. The objective of this project was to offer an alternative approach to plant cultivation that would enable students to cultivate their own ingredients while acquiring practical knowledge in sustainable agriculture. The implementation of this system offers advantages such as achieving self-reliance in food security and enhancing the diversity of food supply systems.

Discussion and Conclusion

The advantages of a hydroponic garden system are manifold, encompassing benefits of an environmental, economic, and social nature. The implementation of such a system enables enhanced resource utilization by minimizing wastage and optimizing yield from every plant or crop cultivated in the culinary kitchen laboratory setting.

Hydroponic cultivation systems present a viable and eco-friendly remedy to the predicaments associated with ingredient procurement in the culinary sector. The integration of a hydroponic garden system within a culinary kitchen laboratory has the potential to yield substantial benefits such as a reduction in water and land usage, increased crop yield, and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices. The present study offers pragmatic recommendations for the installation of a hydroponic system within a culinary laboratory setting, thereby facilitating the ability of chefs and dining establishments to satisfy the increasing need for ecologically sound, regionally procured foodstuffs.

The study's results suggest that culinary institutions and establishments should contemplate the integration of a hydroponic garden system in their kitchen laboratories. This would enable the provision of sustainable plant-based ingredients for recipe development and education. This study centers on the

generation of knowledge and the promotion of social change, with the potential to transform the culinary industry through the adoption of sustainable hydroponics garden systems.

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